

A Comparative Study between Early and Delayed Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy for Acute Calculus Cholecystitis in North East India

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Abstract:

Introduction: Acute cholecystitis is an inflammatory condition commonly caused by gallstones impacted in the cystic duct and surgical approach is mainstay of management. Our objective was to assess and compare pre-operative and post-operative outcomes between early laparoscopic cholecystectomy (ELC); conducted within 72 hours and delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy (DLC); conducted after 72 hours, in acute calculus cholecystitis.

Materials and Methods: The present study was a Prospective comparative study conducted from month of December 2022 to November 2023 at tertiary care centre of Assam state of India. Total 60 patients were included in this study.

Result: ELC was associated with shorter duration of hospital stay (5.7 ± 1.46 days in ELC vs 7.5 ± 1.38 days in DLC) with lesser intraoperative duration (60.5 ± 12.95 minutes in ELC vs 81.1 ± 14.48 minutes in DLC). It was also observed that ELC had less intraoperative blood loss (61.3 ± 18.5 ml in ELC vs 84.3 ± 18.2 ml in DLC) and lesser risk of conversion to open cholecystectomy (10% in ELC vs 20% in DLC).

Conclusion: Based on the findings of the study ELC is safe, time saving feasible and less post operative complications for management of acute calculus cholecystitis preferably performed within 72 hours of duration of onset of symptoms.

Keywords: Early Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy, Delayed Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy, Acute Calculus Cholecystitis, India.

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Introduction

Biliary tract diseases rank among the most common abdominal conditions encountered by surgeons, gastroenterologists, and radiologists in daily practice, second perhaps only to appendicitis, with gallbladder diseases being the most frequently observed within this category with an incidence of 10-15% of population in western societies [1]. Acute cholecystitis is an inflammatory condition typically associated with cholelithiasis and is more prevalent in our population. It is defined as acute inflammation of the gallbladder, commonly caused by gallstones impacted in the cystic duct [2].

Studies on early cholecystectomy as a treatment for acute cholecystitis date back to the 1950s. In 1985,

Prof Dr Erich Mühe of Germany performed the first laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC). In 1970, the first controlled study by Vander linden and Sunzel demonstrated better morbidity and shorter hospital stays after early cholecystectomy.[3]

Initially, laparoscopic cholecystectomy was reserved for selected cases. However, advancements in instrumentation, improved visualization due to new generation cameras and optics, enhanced understanding of the anatomy of the hepato-biliary tree and surrounding structures, and refined surgical skills have enabled surgeons to perform laparoscopic cholecystectomy even in cases of acute cholecystitis, which was previously

considered a relative contraindication. It has now become the preferred procedure for patients presenting with acute cholecystitis, unless technical reasons or safety concerns dictate otherwise [4]

As a result of these events and because of increasing experience and confidence in Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy, the indications were extended to include patients with acute cholecystitis. Several randomized and nonrandomized studies have documented the feasibility and safety of early Laparoscopic cholecystectomy for acute cholecystitis in experienced hands. [5] There is lack of study in north eastern part of India on above topic hence we planned to do study in our tertiary care centre. Our objective was to assess and compare pre - operative and post - operative outcomes between early laparoscopic cholecystectomy (ELC); conducted within 72 hours and delayed laparoscopic cholecystectomy (DLC); conducted after 72 hours, in acute calculus cholecystitis.

Materials and Methods

A prospective observational comparative study of patients aged between 18 to 60 years admitted between December, 2022 to November 2023 with the diagnosis of Acute calculus cholecystitis in the Department of General surgery, Jorhat Medical college and Hospital, Jorhat, Assam, India were recruited. Patients treated with steroids, chemotherapy or immunosuppressive drugs, any obvious septicaemia, choledocholithiasis, pregnant women were excluded. A total of 60 patients who met the inclusion criteria were divided into two groups- Early group (Patient undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy within 72 hours of onset of duration of symptoms) and delayed group (patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy after 72 hours of duration of onset of symptoms).

The diagnosis of acute cholecystitis was based on clinical and ultrasonographic criteria by the surgeon. Both groups were prepared for operation according to the standard protocol of the hospital and relevant data was collected including: demographic data, initial laboratory findings, operation time, post-operative hospital stay, postoperative complications. Both groups underwent laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

After induction of anaesthesia and intubation, the laparoscopic cholecystectomy may begin. First, insufflation of the abdomen is achieved to 15 mmHg using carbon dioxide. Next, four small incisions are made in the abdomen for trocar placement (supraumbilical x1, subxiphoid x1, and right subcostal x2). Utilizing a camera (laparoscope) and long instruments the gallbladder is retracted over the liver. This allows for exposure of the proposed region of the hepatocystic triangle. Careful dissection is carried out to achieve the critical view of safety. This view is defined as (1) clearance of fibrous and fatty tissue from the hepatocystic triangle, (2) the presence of only two tubular structures entering into the base of the gallbladder, and (3) the separation of the lower third of the gallbladder from the liver to visualize the cystic plate. Both structures are carefully clipped and transected. Electrocautery or harmonic scalpel is then used to separate the gallbladder from the liver bed completely. The gallbladder is removed from the abdomen in a specimen pouch. All trocars should be removed under direct visualization and closure of the port site is done.[6]

Results

Total 60 patients underwent laparoscopic cholecystectomy. The Comparison between the two groups in terms of demographics was found to be insignificant. (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic and clinical baseline characteristics of participants

Groups	Sub-Groups	Group A (n=30) ELC Group	Group B (n=30) DLC Group
Gender	Male	09 (30.0%)	11 (36.66%)
	Female	21 (70.0)	19 (63.33%)
Age	Meanage(years)	40.4±12.63	40.75±10.77
Age groups (Years)	18-30	09 (30.0%)	11 (36.66%)
	31-45	13 (43.33%)	12 (40%)
	46-60	8 (26.66%)	7 (23.33%)

In our study, we found that the intraoperative duration mean± standard deviation of 60.5±12.95 minutes for the Early group was shorter than the mean intraoperative time of 81.1±14.48 minutes for the Delayed group ($p < 0.0001$). (Table 2)

Table 2: Distribution and comparison of Mean Operation Time in minutes in both groups

		Number	Mean	SD	Range	Median	p-value
Operation Time in minutes	ELC Group	30	60.5000	12.9555	35.00-90.00	60.0000	<0.0001
	DLC Group	30	81.1667	14.4844	60.00-110.00	80.0000	

Intraoperative blood loss mean± standard deviation of 61.3±18.5 ml for the Early group was lesser than the mean blood loss of 84.3±18.2 ml for the delayed group (p < 0.0001) (Table 3).

Table 3: Distribution and comparison of Mean Blood Loss in ml in both groups

		Number	Mean	SD	Range	Median	p-value
Blood Loss in ml	ELC Group	30	61.3333	18.5199	30.00-100.00	60.0000	<0.0001
	DLC Group	30	84.3333	18.2291	60.00-130.00	80.0000	

We observed lesser rate of conversion to open cholecystectomy (OC) in the early group as compared to delayed group. 03 patients (10%) in the early group and 6 patients (20%) in the delayed group were converted to open procedure. However, the results were statistically insignificant (p value- 0.2780) (Table 4)

Table 4: Distribution and comparison of Type of Surgery from Laproscopic cholecystectomy (LC) to open cholecystectomy (OC) in both groups

Type of Surgery	ELC Group	DLC Group	TOTAL	Statistics analysis
LC	27	24	51	Chi-square value: 1.1765; p-value:0.2780 Odds Ratio:2.220(0.5066,9.9937)
LC to OC	3	6	9	
TOTAL	30	30	60	

The duration of hospital stay mean± standard deviation (SD) of 5.7±1.46 days for the early group is shorter than the delayed group mean± standard deviation (SD) of 7.5±1.38 days(p < 0.0001) (Table 5)

Table 5: Distribution and comparison of Mean Duration of Hospital stays in days in both groups

		Number	Mean	SD	Range	Median	p-value
Duration of Hospital stay in days	ELC Group	30	5.7000	1.4657	4.00-10.00	5.0000	<0.0001
	DLC Group	30	7.5000	1.3834	5.00-10.00	7.0000	

Discussion

In the current study, the mean age of the patient in the early group and delayed group were 41.5 ± 11.07 years and 50.1 ± 8.2 years respectively. The patients in early group were relatively young. Gaurav Gupta et al (2022)[7] in their study found that the mean age in early group was 44.60 ± 14.96 years; in delayed group, it was 46.37 ± 9.23 years. Study conducted by Rati Agrawal et al (2015)[8] found that mean age in early group and delayed group was 47.28±14.57 years and 47.28±14.57 years respectively.

The mean intraoperative blood loss is 61.3±18.5 ml for the early group was significantly lesser than the mean blood loss of 84.3±18.2 ml for the delayed group (p < 0.0001) this findings were consistent with the study conducted by Venkata Sai Sreenivas Uchintala et al (2024)[9] in which the mean blood loss was 27±59 ml for group 1 (within 72 hours) as compared to 59±79 for group 2 (laparoscopic cholecystectomy performed between 4 to 14 days after presentation of symptoms) (p < 0.0001).

In this study the mean duration of operative time is 60.5±12.95 minutes for the early group which is significantly lesser than the delayed group 81.1±14.48 minutes (p < 0.0001). Rahul Chhajer et al (2018)[10] in their study found that Mean duration of surgery was significantly less in early laparoscopic surgery group as compared to delayed laparoscopic surgery group (69.3 versus 108.5 minutes, with p = 0.001).The delayed group not early group required a longer surgical procedure because the adhesions were denser, including fibrosis and necrosis. Similar results were found in the study conducted by Joseph Do Woong Choi et al (2023) [11] which the median operative time was most prolonged in Group 2 (72hours- 1 week, 96.5 minutes) as compared to Group 1 [within 72 hours] (p> 0.05)

In this study the mean duration of hospital stay is 5.7±1.46 days for the early group which was significantly lesser than the delayed group 7.5±1.38 days(p < 0.0001), these findings have also been reported in literature by studies done by

Tom Wiggins, Sheraz R. Markar et al (2019)[12] and Hongsheng Wu et al (2023)[13]

Conclusion

The study suggests that the laparoscopic cholecystectomy performed in early stage is safe and feasible for acute calculus cholecystitis preferably performed within 72 hours of presentation of symptoms (golden period) due to lesser risk of conversion to open procedure and shorter duration of hospital stay without any significant postoperative complications thereby reducing the economic impact to the patient. Early laparoscopic cholecystectomy avoids recurrent symptoms due to multiple episodes of acute cholecystitis and is a definite treatment for cholecystitis in failed conservative management. This can be attributed to increasing experience and technical skill over time, and advancements of laparoscopic instruments and the increasing utilization of laparoscopic subtotal cholecystectomy in the treatment of early acute cholecystitis.

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